

ASSOCIATION BETWEEN COVID-19 DISEASE AND MUCORMYCOSIS THE BLACK FUNGUS

Muhammad Abdullah^{*1}, Ahmad Raza Khan¹, Hasan Ijaz², Sajjad Ahmad³, Saman⁴,
Rimsha Kiran⁵, Meesam Abbas⁶, Sheza Javaid⁷, Sana⁸, Shahzaib Akram⁹

¹Department of Pathology Aga Khan University Hospital

²Faculty of Allied Health Sciences, Department of Pathology, Faisalabad Medical University Faisalabad.

³Department of Allied Health Sciences(Lecturer) Gujrat Institute of Management Science, Gujrat

⁴Institute of Microbiology, Government College University Faisalabad

⁵Faculty of Medical Laboratory Technology, Green international University, Lahore.

⁶Biochemistry and Molecular Biology Comsats University Islamabad

^{7,8,9}Allied Health Sciences Institute, Department of Pathology /Medical Laboratory Technology, Faisalabad Medical University, Faisalabad

¹abdullahnazeer68@gmail.com, ¹ahmadrazakhan028@gamil.com, ²hasanijaz17@gmail.com,

³sajjadkhosa670@gmail.com, ⁴samanansari197@gmail.com, ⁵rimshakiran489@gmail.com

⁶meesam9837@gmail.com, ⁷shezajavaid692@gmail.com, ⁸sanamalik2579@gmail.com,

⁹shahzaibakram786@gmail.com

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Corresponding Author: *

Muhammad Abdullah

Abstract

The Covid-19 pandemic has been a significant threat since 2019. Mucormycosis, a highly fatal fungal infection, is closely associated with Covid-19 because of some treatment methods and underlying risk factors. Covid-19 patients are majorly treated with "Glucocorticoid," and primarily, Covid-19 patients have diabetes, making them vulnerable to mucormycosis. Moreover, Covid-19 patients who do not have enough oxygen called hypoxia make the environment suitable for Mucormycosis growth. Mucormycosis mainly occurs in immune-compromised people. There are other underlying conditions such as malignancy, transplantation, trauma, burns, and surgery that favor the growth of mucormycosis.

INTRODUCTION

In December 2019, a new corona virus (n- COV), severe acute respiratory distress syndrome corona virus 2 (SARS-COV-2), was identified in Wuhan, Central China. Corona virus disease-19 (COVID-19) is highly infectious, which has led to a global pandemic that led to a drastic loss of human life worldwide. From 2019 to 2021, 117M people are infected with corona virus, and nearly 3.38M deaths are reported worldwide. As with the SARS-COV-2, infection with the closely related SARS-COV-2 can cause respiratory disease, which can cause viral pneumonia and acute respiratory failure syndrome (ARI). By the beginning of

December of 2019, the related condition was named the 2019 corona virus disease (COVID-19) (14).

SARS-COV-2 causes corona virus illness (COVID-19), which mostly affects the respiratory system, causing interstitial pneumonia and acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS). The outbreak of COVID-19 caused many difficulties in the diagnosis and routine management of other viral infections. The corona virus (COVID-19) has been linked with a great variety of fungal infections and opportunistic bacterial infections. Recently, many cases of mucormycosis in humans with COVID-19 have been increasingly reported all

over the world. Mucormycosis prevalence rates range from 0.005 to 1.7 per million worldwide (15). The COVID-19 patients are divided into severe and non-severe group. The immune system of the

patients become weak, and the chances of opportunistic infections are increased (27).

Eighty (80) cases of corona virus-associated mucormycosis were reported from eighteen(18)differentcountriesuntilApril12,2021,whichareshownwith"Black" color on the map, and the number of cases from each country is mentioned within the country map (1).

Mucormycosis is a life-threatening fungal infection caused by thread-like fungi of the order Mucorales and class Zygomycetes (2). Mucormycosis is an infection that is mainly caused by a group of filamentous molds (19). Mucormycosis has been reported in COVID-19 patients all over the world. Black fungus is another name of mucormycosis caused mainly by fungi-Rhizopus (16). Mucormycosis is one of the main infections that occur mostly in COVID-19 positive patients. It is difficult to manage COVID-19 with mucormycosis because its spores are spread in the air (28). Mucormycosis is a rare but deadly infection if it is not treated correctly and timely. Mostly it affects immune deficient people and specifically people with diabetes mellitus (3). In advanced countries, mucormycosis mainly infects immune deficient patients with low neutrophils or other defects in the immune system. In contrast, in developing

countries, those patients are mostly infected that are diabetic (19).

The main reason to germinate the spores of mucormycosis in COVID-19 patients is because of its ideal condition and an environment with a low concentration of oxygen (hypoxia), high glucose levels (diabetes mellitus) acid conditions, high iron levels due to immuno suppression, and prolonged hospitalization (15). The occurrence of mucormycosis has been changed in previous years as increased incidence is observed mainly in Asia. Risk factors of mucormycosis vary from region to region; diabetes mellitus is the leading cause of mucormycosis in Asia and Europe. In America, the leading cause is blood cancer and transplant (4). There is few treatment options suggested for COVID-19, but the most effective method is "Glucocorticoid" for covid-19 patients.

Table: Mucormycosis cases in different countries

Countries	No of cases
USA	08
India	42
Pakistan	04
Mexico	04

Iran	02
Russian federation	02
Brazil	01
Turkey	01
California	01

But due to the extensive use of a glucocorticoid, it is resulting in many co-infections like Mucormycosis. One reason for their use is these are cheap and readily available (5). The most common form of mucormycosis is rhino orbital cerebral mucormycosis, and the underlying reason is diabetes mellitus and ketoacidosis (4).

Covid-19 can result in many co-infections which involve both fungal and bacterial infections. It might be due to the irregular immune response or the use of MAB (monoclonal antibodies).

The COVID-19 patients with mucormycosis are usually admitted in ICU and operated with more mechanical ventilation. It is reported that 37% of COVID-19 patients having mucormycosis are admitted in ICU (34). The spores of a different kind of fungus are abundant in the atmosphere, entering through the air passage. When the spores get a suitable environment such as moisture, or the inhaled person is immuno deficient, it can worsen. This infection starts from the interior of the nose and proceeds forward. Another reason or risk factor for developing mucormycosis is the long-term hospitalization and use of ventilators. It is noticed that patients suffering from severe Covid-19 have a low count of T cells (6).

The predisposing factor of mucormycosis is corticosteroid therapy and chronic diseases (31). Mucormycosis can infect different parts of the body like the nasal cavity, oral cavity, brain, lungs, and skin. Mucormycosis can spread from one organ to another, which makes it more dangerous. When the co-infection of mucormycosis occurs with Covid-19, it can be fatal, so Doctors should look for precautions and symptoms to treat it in the early stages and to avoid complications (7). Elevated iron

levels in the body also increase mucormycosis risk as this environment is suitable for their growth (8). Organ transplant such as kidney transplant is another risk factor of mucormycosis. So the most frequent risk factors of mucormycosis are organ transplant, Diabetes mellitus, anti-fungal drugs for an extended period, previous history of Fungal infection (9). According to studies, there is a different prevalence of disease according to underlying condition; according to studies, the people with blood cancer are the most affected, and people with diabetes are at the second number (10). Mucormycosis also depends on the region; the developing countries face more cases than developed countries; in developed countries, the chances are rare, but in developing countries like India, the mucormycosis cases are rare, increasing exponentially have infected a significant population (2).

Mucormycosis or black fungus is mostly seen in India because it is a developing state and unawareness of management (32). The prevalence rate of mucormycosis in India is 80 times higher (0.14 per 1000) than in developed countries. They also need to be aware of the use of invasive mucormycosis, which grows in patients with COVID-19, especially with the help of corticosteroids, even in patients with poorly controlled diabetes mellitus, and in addition to the medical intensive care unit. A positive infection of the cultures of sputum and other respiratory tract specimens should be considered to be relevant for diagnostic testing (15).

Mucormycosis cases in different “INDIAN” states.

During the second wave of corona virus some cases of mucormycosis infection also reported from the different states (33). COVID-19 associated mucormycosis is also seen in kidney transplant patients (9). Mucormycosis is also linked with a higher risk of all-cause mortality and morbidity, depending on the infected area of the body, the nature of the fungus, and the patient's general condition. It is a lethal fungal infection; it is pretty complicated and expensive to treat. A high dose of steroids is prescribed in the severe stage (admitted to hospital) of COVID-19

Patients as a life saver. Steroids depress the immune system (lower CD4 + T and CD8 + T cells) while also combating viral inflammation, resulting in the development of an ideal environment of mucormycosis and other opportunistic infections (16).

Association of mucormycosis with COVID infection causes difficulty in the treatment of corona virus.

The mortality rate is much higher in INDIA (35). AIDS patients are rarely infected by mucormycosis; Mucormycosis is only reported in AIDS patients who used IV drugs. Some people can suffer from mucormycosis even they are not immuno deficient, but the underlying condition in such people is trauma or burn case, which

causes cutaneous mucormycosis. Pulmonary mucormycosis occur in people who have a low neutrophil count (2).

Mucormycosis can be categorized in six forms based on their anatomical locations:

- 1:Rhino-orbital-cerebral mucormycosis (ROCM)
- 2: Pulmonary
- 3:Cutaneous
- 4:Gastro-intestinal(GI)
- 5: Disseminated
- 6:Mucormycosis of un common sites.

Rhino cerebral mucormycosis mostly occurs in diabetic patients. Cutaneous mucormycosis mostly occurs in the allogeneic transplant recipient (29).Disseminated mucormycosis has the highest mortality rate, while mucormycosis of uncommon sites is 65% (22). Around the world, most people are infected with fungal infections, but they recover due to a robust immune system. But after corona virus, the immune power of the people is decreasing, they are more vulnerable to infect with opportunist pathogens. Mucormycosis is one of the infections that affect the COVID-19 patients. It primarily affects corona virus-infected people. But it is quite less common infection only occurs in people whose immune system is weak or have another disease.

Some cases are also seen in healthy people, but it is rare

(25). The outcomes of COVID infection are severe in diabetes patients. The severity of the disease is two times higher in diabetic patients. The diabetic patients have weak immune systems and are vulnerable to mucormycosis, so the immuno deficient and covid-19 positive and infect with mucormycosis have severe clinical symptoms, and the mortality rate is much higher in COVID -19 patients (26). Diabetic persons are more likely to develop rhino-orbital- cerebral mucormycosis (ROCM) (19).

The most significant risk factor for mucormycosis is diabetes and immuno deficient patients; older

age groups are also more likely to develop mucormycosis. But different studies also show that in the absence of risk factors, even young patients might develop mucormycosis as a complication of lung COVID syndrome (17). Mucormycosis infection is strongly linked to increased mortality due to consequences including cavernous sinus thrombosis, disseminated infection, osteomyelitis, and death. Sinuses, skin, and lungs are the main affected areas and can be pretty standard in people suffering or recovering from COVID-19 (15).

Mortality Rate According to Underlying Condition

UNDERLYINGCONDITION	PERCENTAGE
Diabetes	44%
Malignancy	66%
Transplantation	11.5%

COVID-19 causes an abnormal cell-mediated immune response, resulting in the low level of CD4+T cells and CD8+T cells. Such kind of risk factors makes the covid-19 patient vulnerable to co-infections such as mucormycosis. To control mucormycosis, Doctors should have a high level of qualm in patients with immunodeficiency and covid-19 because of history of hospitalization and oxygen support of these patients mostly have other underlying conditions like diabetes and renal failure. As antibiotics and steroids are used to manage covid-19 (11). Antifungal therapy is given to the mucormycosis patients. It is considered effective to control the mortality rate in COVID-19 associated mucormycosis and should be continued until the severe symptoms are sorted out (36).

Major risk factors for Mucormycosis are following:-

- Diabetes mellitus
- Malignancy
- Iron overload
- Organ transplant
- Intravenous drug abuse
- Low neutrophils level
- Low T cell count
- Corticosteroids

- Burn injury

Signs and Symptoms:-

Symptoms of Mucormycosis depend upon the site of fungal infection

Pulmonary Mucormycosis

Symptoms of pulmonary mucormycosis are identical to those of a bacterial infection in patients (37).The primary signs and symptoms of pulmonary mucormycosis are shortness of breath, cough, fever, chest pain, dyspnea, hemoptysis, malaise, weight loss. The serious complication of pulmonary mucormycosis includes crackles in lungs, decrease breath sound, tachypnea, pleural rub, cervical adenopathy, dullness lung percussion and pulmonary collapse (20).

Rhino-cerebral Mucormycosis

One-sided face pain, eyes inflammation, blurred vision, headache, and loss of vision occur. Black necrotic eschar is the distinctive feature of Mucormycosis (2). One of the main clinical findings of rhino-cerebral mucormycosis is the black-colored necrosis of the nasal mucosa, Orbital cellulites, infarction of the brain, Ophthalmoplegia (paralysis or weakness of the eye muscles, multiple cranial nerve palsies, diplopia (21).Headache,

unconsciousness, lesions are also the signs and symptoms of rhino-cerebral mucormycosis infection [\(30\)](#).

Cutaneous Mucormycosis

Skin implantation across erythema is the most typical symptom of determined cutaneous

mucormycosis, which quickly proceeds to necrosis. The main symptoms include mortification, redness, inflammation, purulent discharge (discharge that oozes from a wound), moldy appearance, swelling [\(22\)](#).

Different Sites Affected By Mucormycosis

SITES	PERCENTAGE
Sinuses	39%
Skin	19%
Lungs	24%

Gastro-intestinal mucormycosis

Stomach ache and abdominal pain are the most common gastro-intestinal mucormycosis symptoms, resulting in gastric bleeding and abnormal shift in bowel habits. Sometimes fever is also seen in some patients, but it is rare [\(22\)](#).

Disseminated mucormycosis

The initial symptoms of disseminated mucormycosis are followed by indurate skin nodules and pneumonia [\(23\)](#). The lungs, sinuses, soft tissue, central nervous system, liver, and kidneys are the most common sites of infection. In patients, renal failure, enlargement of both kidneys is seen [\(22\)](#).

Mucormycosis of uncommon sites

Necrotic Facial Eschar of a patient with Rhino -cerebral Mucormycosis [\(2\)](#)

The majority of lesions are found in the basal ganglia. The less common form of mucormycosis includes endocarditis, bone infection, joints infection, inflammation of the peritoneum (peritonitis), and pyelonephritis [\(22\)](#).

Chemical variation in COVID patients

In 2019 corona virus emerges and become pandemic, it gets more attention because of its severity. Different chemical changes occur in COVID patient. About 80% of patients experience

dysgeusia (loss of taste) and **Anosmia** (loss of smell) (38). In severe phase of COVID-19 it is observed that some parameters of the body changed (shown in table). (39) (40)

Parameters	Changes in COVID patients
SGPT	Increases
SGOT	Increases
LDH	Increases
CRP	Increases
Creatinine	Increases
Albumin	Decreases
D-dimer	Increases

Parameters that changes in COVID patients

Diagnosis:-

There are different methods of Mucormycosis diagnosis, but the Gold Standard for Diagnosing Mucormycosis is Biopsy.

■ Direct Examination:-

The direct examination of different fluids to diagnose mucormycosis such as nasal secretions, sputum, and broncho alveolar lavage (BAL) is not reliable (12). Sputum culture has a low sensitivity of 25%, making diagnosis difficult. Broncho alveolar lavage does not produce a higher yield (13).

■ Polymerase chain reaction:-

The Polymerase chain reaction is a reliable and efficient diagnostic assay that would undoubtedly improve results by allowing proper therapy to be started sooner. PCR- based diagnosis is highly efficient and accurate, and it can detect the disease in its initial stages. *CotH* gene is targeted in PCR because it is specifically present in mucoralean fungi (14).

■ Culture:-

The tissue cultures have low sensitivity; to save fungus hyphae from destruction and support their growth, special procedures and skills are required. Additionally, false- positive results can occur due to contamination and the presence of spores in the environment (18).

■ Serology:-

Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA), immuno-blotting, immuno-diffusion test, and enzyme-linked immuno-spot (ELISpot) assays are used to diagnose infection. In patients with disseminated mucormycosis, Mucorales-specific T-cells are detected by enzyme-linked immuno-spot (ELISpot) (24).

Conclusion

COVID-19 patients become immuno suppressed, due to which they become vulnerable to many other opportunistic infections; mucormycosis is one of these infections.

There are many underlying conditions which cause mucormycosis such as malignancy, transplantation, trauma, burns, but in association with COVID-19 diabetes is the main reason of mucormycosis. COVID-19 patients are treated with "Glucocorticoids" which provide suitable environment for the development of mucormycosis, moreover hypoxic environment also favors the development of mucormycosis in COVID-19 patients. Diagnosis of mucormycosis is another problem diagnostic methods available currently are either non-specific or time taking which delays the treatment. Doctors should be hyperconscious to observe the signs and symptoms of mucormycosis in order to treat in early stages. If the mucormycosis is detected in the early stages the infection can be treated with antifungal therapy but, in severe conditions both

antifungal therapy and surgery is required to treat it.

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